

THE ROLE OF PROFILING METHODS IN CREATING THE EMOTIONAL ENVIRONMENT OF THE ADOLESCENT PERSON

Davronov Avazbek Artiqboyevich

Master student of Chirchik state pedagogical university

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Abstract. *Emotional environment is a state provided by changes related to a person's life, activities and forms of self-expression. Creating an emotional atmosphere in the personality of a teenager helps to understand their own life, character, requirements and desires. This helps them to achieve good results in the process of studying and learning. This article presents the author's empirical observations that the method of profiling plays an important role in creating the emotional environment of a teenager.*

Keywords: *emotional environment, profiling, adolescent, psychological tests, psychological interview, psychological questionnaire, non-verbal.*

INTRODUCTION

In the mental processes of adolescents, emotions are characterized by their clear external expression. Emotional changes are so clearly expressed in the external changes of the organism that we can see what characteristics are happening in a person by looking at his appearance, whether he is happy or sad, angry or afraid of something, and similar emotions. we can tell you. External signs of emotions are called expressive actions. Emotsiyalarning tashqi ifodasi turli ko'rinishlarda ro'y beradiki, unda asosiy o'rinni ko'rgazmali jihatlar asosiy o'rin egallaydi.

First, emotions change the work of respiratory organs. For example, the speed and amplitude of breathing increases when pleasant emotions are triggered, decreases when unpleasant emotions prevail, breathing movements accelerate and deepen during excitement, slow down and become shallow during stress, and accelerate during excitement. , and weakens, suddenly speeds up when surprised, slows down when scared, etc.

Changes in breathing in different emotional situations

- a) happy breathing 17 times per minute;
- b) 9 times in active frustration;
- c) 64 times in fear; 12
- d) 40 times when angry.

Secondly, emotion is seen in gestures, facial expressions, that is, in the movements of a person's face and meaningful movements of the whole body.

Thirdly, it includes chemical changes in humoral actions, that is, in the body's blood composition and other fluids, and therefore deeper changes in metabolism.

Therefore, the external expression of emotions includes facial expressions, gestures, changes in appearance and stature, the activity of some exocrine glands, salivation, sweat, and changes in the characteristics of some movements, that is their speed, strength, co-ordination and so on.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the clearest and most obvious expressions of emotions is gathering with laughter. In his works, L. N. Tolstoy described 85 types of looks and 97 types of laughter that represent the mental state of a person. He said, "When a person cries for various reasons, the head and mouth of a person change in different ways." Leonardo da Vinci.

As it can be seen from the pictures made by the Russian psychologist P. M. Yakobson, the appearance of a person mainly depends on the different positions of the lips, eyebrows and eyes, as well as how bright the eyes are. How bright the eye is is determined by the amount of tears and the enlargement of the vessels in the mucous membrane of the eye. The eye visible under the mask has lost its expression. Different positions of the eyes, lips, eyelids, eyebrows, even the human face, make it look different.

The most subtle and powerful means of expressing human emotions are art, especially lyric poems with music, which can literally be called the language of emotions.

A person can deliberately make himself and his body movements, as well as sound, look beautiful. Although he does not forgive certain emotions, he can do actions that express those emotions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Everyone can change the outward expression of their emotions to some extent. Various expressive movements of the body, gestures, especially eye gestures, tone of voice, sadness are important in daily interactions of people. Expressive actions such as a frown, a slight smile, a shrug of the shoulders indicate a person's purpose.

Profiling methods help to determine the psychological portrait of adolescents. These methods include:

1. Tests: These tests are used to analyze the interest in reading and learning, character and other indicators of the adolescent.
2. Psychological interview: This method helps to get information about the problems that occur in reading and learning of adolescents and their forms of self-expression.
3. Psychological Questionnaires: These questionnaires help adolescents analyze their lives, needs and desires.

Profiling plays a very important role in creating an emotional atmosphere. This method helps to learn human emotions, concepts and feelings. If attention should be paid to the emotional environment of a teenager, profiling methods should have the following indicators:

1. Studying non-verbal expressions: By studying a person's facial expressions, hand gestures and other non-verbal expressions, it is possible to understand what emotions a person hides and what concepts he may have.
2. Speech analysis: By analyzing a person's speech, studying his comments, word choice, and language used, it is possible to get information about a person's emotional environment and personality.
3. Study of personal history and professional history: Information about the individual's emotional environment and abilities based on personal history and professional history, including self-development activities, successes and mistakes helps to get

Profiling plays a very important role in creating the emotional environment of a person, and this method facilitates effective communication with a teenager.

CONCLUSION

Profiling plays an important role in creating the emotional environment of a teenager. These tasks consist of analyzing the psychological and complex problems of the adolescent personality, analyzing their youth, gender, nationality, interest in reading and learning, and other indicators. Profiling helps adolescents achieve better academic and academic performance by identifying their personal emotional environment.

Profiling is one of the most important and effective methods for determining the emotional environment of a teenager. This helps young people to achieve better results in reading and learning, and is essential to protect their personal rights and well-being.

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